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MOSAICS WITHIN MOSAICS: THE GEOMETRY OF PORTOLAN ATLASES THAT
CONTRADICTS THE MEDIEVAL ORIGIN HYPOTHESIS

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ABSTRACT

Extensive cartometric analyses were performed on the portolan atlases of Pietro Vesconte (1313), Andrea Bianco (1436), and Battista Agnese (1538), along with their manually assembled composites and contemporaneously made portolan charts. The results indicate that none of the small-scale atlas sheets were fully aligned with the contemporary magnetic north, that they typically exhibit coastline contours mapped to different scales, and that the *spatiums* (50 *miglia* intervals) in Vesconte's and Bianco's atlases differ in length subsequent to the assembly of their composites. Consequently, the atlas sheets could not provide sailors with consistent navigational accuracy across the whole displayed area. Moreover, notable geometric differences can be observed between the composite of Vesconte's atlas and his 1311 portolan chart, as well as between the composite of Bianco's atlas and his smaller-scale chart bound in the same atlas, indicating that their creators had a limited understanding of their geometry. The discovery of cartometrically determined underlying mosaics of subsections encapsulated within their composites with accuracy twice as great—whose spatial extents have remained almost unchanged during more than two centuries of their production and geometrically correspond to portolan charts created before them—suggests that portolan atlases are medieval and early modern copies of earlier-made cartographic sources.

KEYWORDS: portolan atlases, cartometric analysis, portolan chart origins, history of nautical cartography, Toleta de Marteloio

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Umfangreiche kartometrische Analysen wurden an den Portolanatlanten von Pietro Vesconte (1313), Andrea Bianco (1436) und Battista Agnese (1538) sowie an ihren manuell zusammengestellten Kompositen und zeitgleich erstellten Portolankarten durchgeführt. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass keine der kleinmaßstäblichen Atlantenblätter vollständig mit dem zeitgenössischen magnetischen Norden ausgerichtet waren, dass jedes Blatt Küstenlinien zeigt, die auf unterschiedlichen Maßstäben kartiert sind, und dass die *Spatien* (50 *Miglia*-Intervalle) in Vescontes und Biancos Atlanten in der Länge variieren, nachdem ihre Komposite zusammengesetzt wurden. Folglich konnten die Atlansheets den Seeleuten keine konsistente navigationsgenaue Genauigkeit über das gesamte angezeigte Gebiet bieten. Darüber hinaus sind bemerkenswerte geometrische Unterschiede zwischen dem Kompositum von Vescontes Atlas und seiner Portolankarte von 1311 sowie zwischen dem Kompositum von Biancos Atlas und seiner im selben Atlas gebundenen, kleineren Karte zu beobachten, was darauf hinweist, dass ihre Schöpfer ein begrenztes Verständnis ihrer Geometrie hatten. Die Entdeckung kartometrisch bestimmter zugrunde liegender Mosaik von Unterabschnitten, die in ihren Kompositen mit doppelt so großer Genauigkeit eingeschlossen sind—deren räumliche Ausdehnungen sich während der mehr als zweihundertjährigen Produktion kaum verändert haben und geometrisch den vor ihnen erstellten Portolankarten entsprechen—legt nahe, dass Portolanatlanten mittelalterliche und frühneuzeitliche Kopien früherer kartografischer Quellen sind.

SCHLÜSSELWÖRTER: Portolankarten, kartometrische Analyse, Ursprünge der Portolankarten, Geschichte der nautischen Kartographie, Toleta de Marteloio

1. INTRODUCTION: THE ORIGINS DEBATE

Although navigation has been practiced since prehistoric times and the creation of the oldest known navigational aids such as *periploi* (written descriptions of sailing routes) dates back to antiquity,¹ nautical cartography, as far as is known, was established in the western Mediterranean during the late thirteenth and early fourteenth centuries, marked by the sudden appearance of portolan charts and *portolani*—apparent ‘extensions’ of portolan charts in textual form.² The most prominent visual characteristics of portolan charts include networks made of straight colour-coded lines radiating from one or more centres in 32 directions, linear scale bars (still employed in modern cartography), and the apparent absence of a consistent orientation as place names are written perpendicular to the coastline, necessitating the rotation of the chart for full utilisation (Campbell 1987; Monmonier 2004; Edson 2007).

Nevertheless, their most striking feature is the astonishing planimetric accuracy of their coastline renderings, which outperforms any known cartographic antecedent and whose seemingly ‘out of nowhere’ appearance has raised the question of their possible origins for more than a century. From a scholarly standpoint, there are two main hypotheses regarding the origins of portolan charts. One hypothesis, primarily based on a descriptive approach, contends that the geometry of portolan charts was directly derived from bearing- and distance-measurements obtained by sailors in the late medieval period (Fischer 1886; Kretschmer 1909; Stevenson 1911; Taylor 1951a, 1951b; Pujades 2007; Gaspar 2007, 2008, 2023), whereas the other hypothesis, established by comparing the results of quantitative (cartometric) analyses with known historical sources, assumes that portolan charts are too accurate to be genuine late medieval products and that the spatial data supporting their geometry was likely acquired at an earlier period.³ The term *cartometric (method)* was conceived in the late nineteenth century by Hermann Wagner, who pioneered it and established that portolan charts are mosaic images composed of sub-charts made in a cylindrical projection, whose map scale and (anticlockwise) tilts are variable across the chart field on a regional basis. Wagner proposed the hypothesis that the spatial data upon which their coastlines are rendered were acquired before the late Middle Ages (Wagner 1896 (1969): 478, 480–483). One of the most extensive and detailed studies of portolan charts was conducted by Scott A. Loomer and published in his doctoral thesis. He cartometrically analysed 26 portolan charts by georeferencing each one to nine different map projections of a modern map and concluded that their geometry is most similar to the Mercator projection (Loomer 1987: 144–146, 166–167). In his 2014 doctoral thesis, Roel Nicolai cartometrically analysed five portolan charts using a slightly different methodological approach and confirmed their high geometric similarity to a modern map in Mercator projection. His analysis also reveals that portolan charts are composed of sub-charts varying in scale and orientation, aiming at their pre-medieval origin (Nicolai 2014: 169–270, 401–410). In 2024, Tome Marelič published two cartometric studies in which he examined seven portolan charts and two portolan atlas composites. His findings show that considerable portions of coastline contours on some of the oldest known portolan charts—the *Carte Pisane*, *Cortona chart*, and two Pietro Vesconte’s charts—were drawn nearly identically, assuming their common origin (Marelič 2024a: 142–151). Moreover, the analysis reveals that all the examined portolan charts and atlases are mosaic-images made of subsections that differ from each other in terms of rotation and scale, that the spatial extents of particular subsections are similar among charts, and that their planimetric accuracy is, on average, twice as high as the accuracy of their unity (a portolan chart or an atlas). His hypothesis suggests that there is a high likelihood that those elements represent copies of some earlier-made cartographic material that late medieval cartographers failed to assemble properly (Marelič 2024a: 151–155, 2024c: 11–15). According to the author’s knowledge, it is the first cartometric analysis of portolan atlases in general, but the atlases in that study (Marelič 2024c) were analysed exclusively as composites. In order to understand their geometry in more detail, it is necessary to conduct individual cartometric analyses of their sheets as well.

¹ Some of the oldest known *periploi* are *The Periplus of Pseudo-Scylax* (c. fourth century BC) and *Stadiasmus Maris Magni* (c. third century) (Taylor 1957: 50–52; Shipley 2011: 1–8).

² *Liber de Existencia Riveriarum et Forma Maris nostri Mediterranei* from the early thirteenth century (Gautier Dalché 1995) and *Lo Compasso de Navegare* from the late thirteenth century represent some of the earliest such documents (Motzo 1947; Debanne 2011).

³ It is crucial to highlight that the late medieval and early modern production period of the preserved physical samples in terms of the age of their carrier material (parchment sheets made from livestock skin) and the cartographic content drawn on them is not in question in any way because it was established either through radiocarbon dating (Hofmann et al., 2016, according to Livieratos & Boutoura 2018) or through explicit writings by their authors.

2. SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY

In contrast to portolan charts, which show the usual territorial coverage from the Atlantic coasts of West Europe and Northwest Africa to the Black Sea as a single cartographic unit, portolan atlases display these same areas as segmented and distributed across multiple physically detached sheets of vellum. The primary objective of this research is to quantitatively determine the metrics of three portolan atlases made by Pietro Vesconte (1313), Andrea Bianco (1436), and Battista Agnese (1538) (Table 1), utilising four parallel approaches whose results were subsequently compared. The first approach focuses on the standalone geometry of their physical constituents by subjecting each of their sheets to its own individual cartometric analysis. The second approach focuses on the geometry of the union of their geographical content in such a way that the atlas sheets were graphically joined into composites, which were then cartometrically analysed as standalone units.⁴ The third approach is the comparison of atlas geometry to the geometry of portolan charts made by the same authors, whereas the fourth approach involves an intercomparison of doubly charted sub-basins made to different map scales.

Table 1. Information regarding the research sample.

DESCRIPTION:	TYPE:	TERRITORIAL COVERAGE:	DIMENSIONS [mm]:	APPROX. MAP SCALE:*	IDENTICAL POINTS:
Pietro Vesconte's portolan chart (1311) <i>Archivio di Stato di Firenze, CN 01</i>	chart	Central and East Mediterranean, Black Sea	632×483	1:5,390,000	296
	atlas sheet	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, West Mediterranean	480×412	1:5,320,000	177
		Adriatic Sea inset (drawn far to the west)			49
Pietro Vesconte's portolan atlas (1313) , <i>Bibliothèque nationale de France, département Cartes et plans, CPL GE DD-687 (RES)</i>	atlas sheet	Central Mediterranean, Ligurian Sea, Tyrrhenian Sea, Ionian Sea	469×403	1: 4,130,000	138
	atlas sheet	Aegean Sea (large scale)	467×403	1: 2,105,000	57
	atlas sheet	East Mediterranean, S Aegean Sea	473×406	1: 4,040,000	83
	atlas sheet	Black Sea, Sea of Marmara, Sea of Azov	480×419	1: 4,010,000	66
	atlas composite	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, whole Mediterranean, Black Sea	1077×483	variable across the composite	433**
	chart	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, whole Mediterranean, Black Sea	395×267	1: 14,750,000	378**
Andrea Bianco's portolan atlas (1436) , <i>Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana, Ms. It. Z, 76 (=4783)</i>	atlas sheet	Atlantic coast of W Europe	394×271	1: 5,790,000	63
	atlas sheet	Atlantic coast of NW Africa, Alboran Sea	399×281	1: 5,720,000	103
	atlas sheet	West & Central Mediterranean, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea	392×267	1: 6,360,000	212
	atlas sheet	Central & East Mediterranean, Ionian Sea, Aegean Sea	393×273	1: 6,390,000	127
	atlas sheet	Black Sea, Sea of Marmara, Sea of Azov	395×267	1: 4,620,000	57
	atlas composite	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, whole Mediterranean and Black Sea	814×490	variable across the composite	455**
	atlas sheet	Atlantic coast of W Europe		1: 5,200,000	65
Battista Agnese's portolan atlas (1538) , <i>University of Pennsylvania, Rare Book & Manuscript Library, LJS 28</i>	atlas sheet	Atlantic coast of NW Africa, West Mediterranean		1: 5,260,000	181
	atlas sheet	Central & East Mediterranean, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Aegean Sea	570 × 398	1: 5,220,000	308** (182)***
	atlas sheet	Adriatic Sea (large scale)		1: 1,820,000	
	atlas sheet	Aegean Sea (large scale)		1: 1,800,000	68
	atlas sheet	Black Sea, Sea of Marmara, Sea of Azov		1: 5,140,000	55
	atlas composite (small scale only)	Atlantic coast of W Europe and NW Africa, whole Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	1088×637	variable across the composite	469**
	atlas composite (small & large scale)		1088×637		478**

* The approximate map scales were computed with the assumed *portolan mile* value of 1.25 km.

** The number of control points across the atlas composite for the Mediterranean and Black Sea area only.

*** Atlas sheet was georeferenced with the exclusion of the control points across its Adriatic and Aegean Sea areas.

⁴ Although the geometry of Bianco's and Agnese's atlas composites was already analysed in Marelič's study (Marelič 2024c), the paper does not provide a detailed explanation of their construction, and their cartometrically determined subsections were not explicitly rendered as their overlays.

The preparation of each atlas sheet for georeferencing, including the rectification of their digital reproductions and identification of their identical points, came to be a relatively simple task in comparison to their graphical assembly into coherent composites to be georeferenced as standalone cartographic units. Portolan charts exhibit one or more linear scale bars positioned across the chart field, calibrated in such a way that one interval (*spatium*) represents 50 *miglia*, a distance unit usually referred to as a *portolan mile*⁵ whose length, estimated at about 1.25 km (Campbell 1987: 389), was never fully resolved. Moreover, the north Atlantic coasts have consistently been rendered to a relatively smaller scale, whereas the areas on their eastern fronts were rendered to a relatively larger scale (Wagner 1896 (1969): 481; Nicolai 2014: 259–262; Marelić 2024a: 141, 154, 2024c: 12–14), which presents a challenge to the reliability of its reconstruction and raises doubts about cartographers' true understanding of its length or even the geometry of portolan charts as a whole. Because of the typical structural map-scale inconsistencies of portolan charts and because certain atlas sheets were intentionally drawn to larger scales (like the Aegean and Adriatic Seas), all the composites were assembled in such a way that their sheets showing the Central Mediterranean were kept in their original size, whereas the sizes of the remaining sheets were adjusted to fit them. The initial expectation was that their coastline contours would fit each other well once the lengths of their linear scale-bar intervals were adjusted to match in relative terms (regardless of true *portolan mile* length). Agnese's atlas, made nearly three centuries after the creation of the first known portolan charts, is the only one whose lengths of map scale intervals size-wise align with its coastline renderings, whereas Vesconte's atlas, in a sense, represents the 'worst-case scenario' (assembly method A in Figure 1). Due to the emergence of this additional layer of map scale inconsistencies, all three atlas composites were created by minimising the graphical conflicts between the coastline contours of the neighbouring sheets (assembly method C in Figure 1), regardless of whether or not this led to the mutual accord of their scale-bar lengths.

The geometric properties of both standalone atlas sheets and atlas composites were computed using the same methodological approach that stems from cartometric analysis and involves a series of consecutive steps. The initial step is to identify the sufficient number of *identical points*⁶ per sheet and composite to be joined to their corresponding *reference points* on a modern map representing locations (such as ports, river mouths, or capes) whose spherical coordinates are known and treated as error-free. Georeferencing, the process of pairing identical points on charts with their reference equivalents on a modern map and performed in GIS software, involves computing its *least-squares estimation (LSE)* under optimal scale and rotation. The goal is to achieve the best fit between the geometry of the portolan atlas sheet (or composite) and a reference modern map. In this research, atlas sheets and composites were georeferenced to a map in Mercator projection with the application of a 4-parameter Helmert similarity transformation (Modenov & Parkhomenko 1965: 77–93) by which both their axes (*X* and *Y*) are scaled and rotated uniformly, providing that the geometry of the georeferenced units remains true to the original in relative terms. Since portolan atlas sheets and composites geometry-wise differ from the reference map to a certain degree, the 'aftermath' of the process is a set of (projected) positional displacements of their identical points (*dX* and *dY* in kilometres) called *residuals*. To cancel out the distance distortions induced by the reference map projection, those projected displacements were de-projected (*dλ* and *dφ* in degrees), and their angular displacements were converted into corresponding geodesic distances on the surface of the WGS84 ellipsoid (*dLON* and *dLAT* arcs in kilometres). The end result is the computation of their axial *root mean-square error* values (*RMSE dLON*, and *RMSE dLAT*), with the larger value being used to indicate the planimetric accuracy of atlas sheets and composites (Jenny & Humi 2011: 403–405; Nicolai 2014: 209–210; Penzkofer 2016: 27–28).⁷ Georeferencing of the atlas composites reveals that certain portions of coastlines relatively differ in terms of their rotations, shifts, and map scales in comparison to the reference map, which induced an additional approach to the study of their metrics. In accordance with the varying distribution of magnitudes and orientation of residuals on a regional level, which was also observed on the portolan charts (Marelić 2024a: 143, 145–151, 2024c: 5), atlas composites were segmented into cartometrically determined *subsections*, each of which was, in addition, georeferenced individually (see their colour-coded vectorized coastlines in Figure 2). This allowed for the computation of the subsections' standalone metrics, which are covered in more detail in the following chapters.

⁵ The information that one *spatium* contains 50 *miglia* was derived from a now-destroyed chart made in the early fourteenth century by Giovanni de Carignano and Vesconte de Maiolo's chart from 1512 (Nordenskiöld 1897: 22; Winter 1956: 43–44), and can be found in the *Tondo e Quadro* diagram in Andrea Bianco's portolan atlas (Figure 11).

⁶ The number of *identical points* identified on each cartometrically analysed unit is listed in the rightmost column of Table 1.

⁷ Planimetric accuracy increases with smaller *RMSE* values, and vice versa.

A: composite assembly according to the lengths of linear scale bars (relative to the Central Mediterranean sheet)

- western sheet
- Central Mediterranean sheet
- Adriatic Sea inset (from the western sheet)
- Aegean Sea sheet
- East Mediterranean sheet
- Black Sea sheet

 areas of a relatively poor fit of coastline contours

B: composite assembly according to the coastline contours of Vesconte's 1311-13 composite (relative to the Central Mediterranean sheet)

C: composite assembly according to atlas' coastline contours (relative to the Central Mediterranean sheet)

Figure 1. Methods for assembling the composite of Pietro Vesconte's 1313 atlas (only method C provides their coherent composite). Chart source: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, CPL GE DD-687 (RES).

3. PIETRO VESCONTE'S PORTOLAN ATLAS (1313)

In 1311, Pietro Vesconte created the oldest known portolan chart (Figure 3), whose authorship and the year of production were explicitly inscribed on its vellum sheet,⁸ whereas in 1313, he made the earliest known portolan atlas, comprised of five sheets with variable map scales and the graphical design of their scale bars (Figure 1, Table 1). The *Central Mediterranean*, *Aegean Sea*, and *Black Sea* sheets, as well as his 1311 chart, contain scale bars designed as encircled crosses, whereas the scale bars on the *western sheet* and the *East Mediterranean sheet* are linear and more simplistic in design (see their colour-coded vectorized tracings in Figure 1). Several of these illustrations appear to have been drawn with a relatively low level of consistency, or they were left partially incomplete due to the fact that they are missing some of their *spatia* subdivisions (10 *miglia* intervals).

A more detailed approach reveals that Vesconte was either somewhat careless in illustrating the scale bars across the atlas sheets or that his knowledge about the geometric properties of charts and their map scale was insufficient for two reasons. The first reason is that its coastal contours exhibit noticeably poor alignment when atlas sheets are resized to make all of their scale bars the same length, with the largest discrepancy occurring between the *western* and *Central Mediterranean* sheets (assembly method A in Figure 1). The second reason is metrics-wise related to his 1311 chart, whose 'western appendix' can be found on the *western sheet* in his 1313 atlas, both in terms of territorial coverage and in terms of their map scale. Namely, the average *spatium* length on his 1311 chart (11.6 mm) is nearly identical to that of the *western sheet* in his 1313 atlas (11.8 mm). However, when coastline renderings on his 1311 chart are used as a template, it is also not possible to create a composite devoid of graphical conflicts between the neighbouring sheets (assembly method B in Figure 1), and the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov on his 1311 chart seem to have been drawn to a scale that is approximately 12% larger compared with his 1313 atlas. Since both approaches yielded a relatively poor coastline fit, the only feasible method was to adjust the size and rotation of its sheets by joining their coastline contours as smoothly as possible (assembly method C in Figure 1), whose byproducts only strengthened the suspicion regarding Vesconte's insight into its metrics. For example, its *western sheet* has to be enlarged to 155% of its size, elongating its *spatiums* by 27% in comparison to the *Central Mediterranean sheet*. Also, the *Adriatic Sea inset* has to be equally enlarged and rotated 5° anticlockwise to properly fit the *Central Mediterranean sheet*, whereas the *East Mediterranean sheet* has to be rotated 1.2° anticlockwise.

Individual georeferencing of Vesconte's atlas sheets reveals that each of them exhibits a different *LSE*-computed clockwise rotation (θ_{LSE}), spanning from 6.5° to 11.9° (the upper part of Figure 2), whereas their composite becomes rotated by 11.6° clockwise.⁹ The less prominent rotation of the *Adriatic Sea inset* is affected by Vesconte's plotting error of 5° mentioned above—if it had not been the case, the inset would have exhibited a clockwise rotation of 11.5°. Nevertheless, the end result is far from a coherent composite because of significant gaps and crossings between the neighbouring coastline renderings. Its *western sheet* shows the most inaccurate fit to the reference map because its North Atlantic coasts, made by Vesconte to a significantly smaller map scale, comprise 74 out of 177 of its identical points (42%), and, therefore, negatively affect its accuracy estimation by enlarging its image¹⁰ and shifting it northwest. The average planimetric accuracy of its sheets with the inclusion of the *western sheet* (20.5 km) is 1.45 times greater than the accuracy of its manually assembled composite georeferenced across its Mediterranean and Black Sea areas (29.8 km). However, the average accuracy of its eight cartometrically derived subsections (the lower part of Figure 2) is 13.5 km, or 2.2 times greater.

⁸ *Petrus Vesconte de Janua fecit ista carta ann[o] dni MCCCXI*, meaning *Pietro Vesconte of Genoa made this chart in 1311* (Nordenskiöld 1897: 57).

⁹ Terminological clarification: The coastal renderings on portolan atlases and charts show anticlockwise tilts with respect to geographic north (Figure 1), according to which their georeferenced images get their (*LSE*-computed) clockwise rotations (Figure 2).

¹⁰ If the georeferenced image of an atlas sheet or a composite subsection becomes proportionally enlarged relative to one of its sheets or subsections (the *Central Mediterranean* in this study, whose relative scale is displayed as 100%), it means that it has been originally made to a smaller scale, and vice versa.

Figure 2. The overlay of individually georeferenced sheets from Pietro Vesconte's 1313 atlas with the vectorized coastline of their coherent composite (the upper part) and the overlay of the coherent composite with the vectorized coastlines of its cartometrically determined subsections (the lower part). Chart source: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, CPL GE DD-687 (RES). Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al. 2017).

In addition, the composite of Vesconte's atlas without its *western sheet* was georeferenced in parallel with his 1311 chart, with whom it shares its territorial extent. The planimetric accuracy of its reduced composite (30.4 km) is slightly poorer in comparison to his 1311 chart (27.1 km), whereas their *LSE*-computed rotations differ by 1.3° . Figure 3 illustrates numerous differences between his two works that affect their planimetric accuracy on a regional basis. Since Vesconte created both cartographic units only two years apart and since the *western sheet* in his atlas scale-wise fits better with his 1311 chart, these discrepancies additionally prove that he was most likely unaware of their existence and that his attention to the planimetric accuracy of his charts was lower than expected.

Figure 3. Noticeable geometric differences between Pietro Vesconte's georeferenced chart (1311) and the georeferenced coherent composite of his 1313 atlas (with the exclusion of its *western sheet*). The annotations are colour-coded to indicate which unit exhibits more pronounced deviations in a certain region. Chart source: *Archivio di Stato di Firenze*, CN 01. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al. 2017).

4. ANDREA BIANCO'S PORTOLAN ATLAS (1436)

In 1436, more than a century after Vesconte, Andrea Bianco created an atlas comprised of five sheets (the upper part of Figure 4), one small-scale portolan chart (Figure 5), one circular *mappa mundi*¹¹, one *Ptolemaic map* of the *oikoumene* made in Ptolemy's first projection,¹² and the graphical version of *Toleta de Marteloio*.¹³ Apart from being a co-author of the well-known *Fra Mauro map* (a circular planisphere that carries portolan chart aesthetics) made around 1450, Andrea Bianco was an experienced sailor and senior galley officer, and there are more than fifty historical entries of his voyages across the Mediterranean and beyond, spanning from the Black Sea in the east to London in the northwest (Campbell 1987: 432–433; Edson 2007: 1–10, Pujades 2007: 496).

To create a coherent composite of Bianco's atlas relative to its *West and Central Mediterranean sheet* (the lower part of Figure 4), none of the remaining sheets need to be resized except for the *Black Sea sheet*, which was intentionally made to a 37.5% larger map scale and, therefore, has to be reduced to 72.7% of its original size. However, this smoothly joined composite exhibits smaller variations regarding the map scale on its western front in such a way that the average *spatium* lengths of its *North Atlantic sheet* and *South Atlantic and Alboran Sea sheet* are 10.8 mm and 10.9 mm, respectively (about 110% relative to the *West and Central Mediterranean sheet* with an average *spatium* length of 9.8 mm). It seems unlikely that Bianco intentionally made them to a slightly larger scale or even that he possessed in-depth knowledge about their true map scales at all, because after their individual georeferencing is done, their relative map scales (relative to the *West and Central Mediterranean sheet*) are 83.3% and 97.1%, respectively. Similarly to Vesconte's atlas, individual georeferencing of Bianco's atlas sheets cannot provide a coherent composite due to the graphical conflicts of their coastlines caused by variations

¹¹ Medieval manuscript maps on which the religious interpretations of the known world were shown (Woodward 1987: 286–291).

¹² *Ptolemaic maps* are late medieval and early modern reconstructions of the now-lost cartographic content of Claudius Ptolemy's *Geography* (Gautier Dalché 2007: 285–287). The closest modern equivalent of *Ptolemy's first projection* is the equidistant conic projection with the standard latitude $\phi_0=36^\circ\text{N}$; the parallel of Rhodes (Keuning 1955: 9–10; Snyder 1993: 5–8).

¹³ Trigonometry tables that were supposedly made to assist sailors during navigation. *Toleta de Marteloio* in textual form is a part of Gratius Benincasa's portolan made in 1470 (Kretschmer 1909: 358–359).

in their *LSE*-computed rotations and their relative shifts (the upper part of **Figure 4**). Their average planimetric accuracy (19.1 km) is 1.4 times greater than the accuracy of their composite georeferenced across the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas (26.8 km), whereas the average accuracy of its eight cartometrically derived subsections (the lower part of **Figure 4**) is 14.1 km, or 1.9 times greater.

Figure 4. The overlay of individually georeferenced sheets from Andrea Bianco’s 1436 atlas with the vectorized coastline of their coherent composite (the upper part) and the overlay of the coherent composite and its vectorized coastline with the vectorized coastlines of its cartometrically determined subsections (the lower part). Chart source: *Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana, Ms. It. Z, 76 (=4783)*. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al. 2017).

The comparison of Bianco’s atlas composite with his portolan chart (**Figure 5**) that has been made to a significantly smaller scale (**Table 1**) and bound in the same atlas, conducted by georeferencing both units across

their Mediterranean and Black Sea areas, reveals significant planimetric differences between the two. First, the estimated accuracy of his composite (26.8 km) is significantly greater than the accuracy of his small-scale chart (36.2 km). Second, his atlas composite is more accurate longitude-wise, whereas his small-scale chart is more accurate latitude-wise, mainly because considerable portions of its coastlines exhibit excessive longitudinal shifts and inappropriate map scales.

Figure 5. Noticeable geometric differences between Andrea Bianco's georeferenced small-scale portolan chart (1436) and the georeferenced coherent composite of his 1436 atlas. The annotations are colour-coded to indicate which unit exhibits more pronounced deviations in a certain region. Chart source: *Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana*, Ms. It. Z, 76 (=4783). Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al. 2017).

5. BATTISTA AGNESE'S PORTOLAN ATLAS (1538)

Battista Agnese authored numerous portolan charts and atlases in the first half of the sixteenth century (Astengo 2007: 178, 181–182; Krtalić 2022: 20–22), nearly three centuries after the emergence of the earliest portolan charts. His 1538 atlas, made more than two centuries after Vesconte's, consists of four sheets made to a smaller scale that fully encompass the usual portolan chart territorial coverage (the upper part of Figure 6), and two 'additional' large-scale sheets showing the Adriatic and Aegean Seas (the lower part of Figure 6). For research purposes, two composites of his atlas were assembled: one made only of the small-scale sheets and the other with large-scale sheets placed over them. Their assembly into a smoothly joined composite is fairly easy because there is no need for resizing the small-scale sheets (relative to its *Central and East Mediterranean sheet*), whereas large-scale sheets need to be reduced to 35% of their original size.

Since all the *spatiums* are equal in size across both coherent composites, the initial assumption (on a superficial level at least) would be that Agnese possessed an accurate body of bearing- and distance-data and was well aware of the scale-metrics of his atlas—a reasoning that is solidly refuted by the cartometric evidence. For example, the greatest planimetric accuracy of its *North Atlantic sheet* and *South Atlantic and West Mediterranean sheet* is obtained when their map scale is 77.1% and 94.5% relative to the scale of the *Central and East Mediterranean sheet* (with an average *spatium* length of 12.0 mm), respectively. Also, as in the two previous atlases, each sheet exhibits its own *LSE*-computed rotation, meaning that their individual georeferencing cannot provide a coherent composite either. The most interesting fact regarding their rotations is that, while the *Central and East Mediterranean sheet* alone (with the exclusion of control points across the Adriatic and Aegean Seas) becomes rotated 10.9° clockwise, the large-scale sheets of those areas become rotated by 7.5° and 9.3°, respectively (the lower part of Figure 6).

Figure 6. Individually georeferenced small-scale sheets (the upper part) and small- and large-scale sheets (the lower part) from Battista Agnese’s 1538 atlas and the overlay of their vectorized coastlines with the coastlines of their coherent composites. Chart source: University of Pennsylvania, Rare Book & Manuscript Library, LJS 28. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al. 2017).

The average planimetric accuracy of its four small-scale sheets (19.4 km) is 1.6 times greater than the accuracy of their composite georeferenced across the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas (32.1 km), whereas the average accuracy of its eight cartometrically derived subsections (Figure 7) is 15.6 km, or 2.1 times greater. Interestingly, the planimetric accuracy of Agnese’s composite, only made of small-scale sheets (32.1 km), is slightly greater in comparison to the composite that includes his large-scale renderings of the Adriatic and Aegean Seas (33.1 km). This finding implies that there is no connection between the scale and accuracy of the charts, meaning that increasing the scale of the charts did not necessarily enhance their accuracy.

Figure 7. The overlay of a coherent composite of small-scale sheets from Battista Agnese's 1538 atlas with the vectorized coastlines of its cartometrically determined subsections. Chart source: *University of Pennsylvania, Rare Book & Manuscript Library, LJS 28*. Basemap shapefile source: *marineregions.org (Claus et al. 2017)*.

6. THE ANATOMY OF ATLAS SHEETS

The most prominent visual effect of individual georeferencing of portolan atlas sheets is that it produces 'broken portolan chart images' due to differences in their *LSE*-computed rotations and scales. The predominant scholarly opinion regarding the anticlockwise tilts of portolan chart coastlines is that it is an explicit imprint of contemporary magnetic declination values across the charted area (Pujades 2007: 514; Gaspar 2023: 3, 6–12). In short, the hypothesis assumes that the late medieval sailors conducted numerous voyages across the Mediterranean, west European, and northwest African Atlantic coasts, during which they used their magnetic compasses to track the bearings of routes with high accuracy, simultaneously unaware that their observations were affected by the (easterly) magnetic declination. Those bearing-observations (together with distance-observations) were, supposedly, meticulously recorded and compiled into navigational logs, which were then submitted to cartographers, who converted them into graphical frameworks—whether portolan charts or atlases.

In contrast, the cartometric analyses of the examined atlas sheets and their composites suggest that there is no solid connection between their anticlockwise tilts (indicated by their *LSE*-computed clockwise rotations) and the contemporary values of magnetic declination derived from the CALS3k.4 paleomagnetic model (Korte & Konstable 2011), sampled across regions that correspond to the extents of their subsections (Figure 8). The individual rotation values of atlas sheets are mostly not in accordance with the regional distribution of the magnetic declination from the period of their creation. One exception are the *western sheet* and *Central Mediterranean sheet* in Vesconte's atlas, whose rotations (8.9° and 9.3°, respectively) are similar to contemporary magnetic declination across the West Mediterranean (9.0°). However, its north and south Atlantic coastlines, drawn on the *western sheet* and rotated altogether by 8.9° as well, show a significant offset in comparison to contemporary declination values across these particular areas. Another exception is the *West and Central Mediterranean sheet* in Bianco's atlas, seemingly aligned with the magnetic north across the Central Mediterranean and Adriatic Sea areas but not across the West Mediterranean. Sheets from Agnese's atlas—made in the period during which the mariner's compass was most developed and most frequently used (compared to earlier atlases)—show the greatest deviations from the magnetic declination of that era, and neither of his small-scale sheets is aligned with the contemporary magnetic north on a regional level. It is unlikely that their geometry is a direct consequence of numerous compass-measurements carried out prior to their original creation because these results demonstrate that at the time of their creation, not a single sheet (from any of the three examined atlases) could have been used

in its entirety for evenly accurate navigation with the use of a magnetic compass, especially the sheets showing the areas far east.

Another difficulty for navigation with the use of portolan atlas sheets is their inconsistent map scale (Figure 9). Boxes connected by solid lines represent scale differences exhibited by the individually georeferenced sheets (relative to sheets on which the Central Mediterranean is shown, displayed as 100%) if the starting point of their intercomparison is a coherent composite in which discrepancies between their *spatiums* in individual cases are taken into account (assembly method C in Figure 1). The results show that areas to the west have been rendered to a relatively smaller scale (especially the North Atlantic coasts), whereas areas to the east have been rendered to a relatively larger scale. In the cases of Vesconte's and Bianco's atlases, there is another dataset that represents their relative scale differences if the starting point for their comparison is the equalisation of their *spatiums* (assembly method A in Figure 1). It is not a correct approach because such a method cannot provide coherent composites, and there are two reasons for which it is plotted on the diagram on purpose. The first one is to additionally highlight the cartographers' relatively poor insight into actual distances across the displayed areas. The second one is to explicitly demonstrate how cartographers' seemingly careless approach to illustrating scale bars can adversely affect their intercomparison. If the late medieval and early modern sailors had continuously measured the distance sailed with high accuracy and regularly supplied the cartographers with those datasets, the coastal renderings in the portolan atlases would probably have become more and more harmonised in terms of map scale over time, especially in cases of *North Atlantic sheets* in Bianco's and Agnese's atlases. If they had possessed freshly acquired distance-data, they should have been able to properly adjust the (standalone) map scale of that area because it has been rendered on physically separate pieces of vellum. Therefore, it seems unlikely that these differences arose from the compilation of the numerous shipborne distance-measurements that were carried out before these atlases were produced.

The third and most significant geometric parameter of portolan atlases is the high average planimetric accuracy of their sheets, ranging between 19.1 km (Bianco's atlas) and 20.5 km (Vesconte's atlas) (Figure 10). The least accurate unit is the *western sheet* from Vesconte's atlas (49.2 km) because its North Atlantic coasts—made to a significantly smaller scale—negatively affect its accuracy estimation and, in extenso, the average accuracy of the entire atlas. Without the *western sheet* (encompassing the South Atlantic and West Mediterranean as well), its average accuracy is 14.7 km, which is a higher value compared to the remaining two atlases' sheets covering the same areas. Namely, the average accuracy of Bianco's atlas (without its *North Atlantic sheet* and *South Atlantic and Alboran Sea sheet*) is 20.6 km, whereas the accuracy of Agnese's atlas (without its *North Atlantic sheet* and *South Atlantic and West Mediterranean sheet*) is 22.6 km. Since the *western sheet* in Vesconte's atlas contains only one scale bar whose *spatiums* fit its southern regions better, and since the accuracy of its *North Atlantic subsection* is fairly high (19.6 km), it seems more likely that Vesconte copied that piece of coastline from some older source, unaware that he made it to a map scale that is too small.

Figure 8. Rotational values for individually georeferenced atlas sheets, the manually assembled atlas composites (georeferenced across their Mediterranean and Black Sea areas), and their individually georeferenced subsections in comparison to magnetic declination values for years 1300, 1400, and 1500 according to the CALS3k.4 paleomagnetic model. CALS3k.4 data source: [GEOMAGIA50.v3.2](#), accessed: March 18, 2023.

Figure 9. Map scale differences between individually georeferenced portolan atlas sheets relative to the sheet containing the Central Mediterranean area (shown as 100%) and map scale differences between individually georeferenced portolan atlas subsections relative to their *Central Mediterranean subsections* (shown as 100% as well, although in absolute terms they do not correspond to map scales of their sheets containing the Central Mediterranean area).

Figure 10. RMSE accuracy values of individually georeferenced atlas sheets, the manually assembled atlas composites (georeferenced across their Mediterranean and Black Sea areas), and their individually georeferenced subsections.

6.1. HARDLY ASSUMABLE LENGTH OF THE PORTOLAN MILE

Apart from the already mentioned *portolan mile* (*miglio*) length of 1.25 km, there are other assumptions asserted by other authors. Wagner assumed its length to be about 1.22 km, with the exception of the area between Sardinia and Malta, where he computed its length of 1.42 km (Wagner 1896 (1969): 479). James E. Kelley Jr. argues that across the West Mediterranean, *miglio* was considered equal to 5000 palms (where a palm equals $\frac{3}{4}$ of the length of a foot) and that the length of a palm itself (as a fundamental unit) differed across that region. He also states that the *miglio*, made of 5000 Genoese feet, which he associates with Francesco Beccari’s portolan chart (1403), has a length of 1.34 km (Kelley 1979: 18–19). According to Hans C. Freiesleben, there were two different *miglio* values in use—the shorter one used in the Mediterranean (1.25 km) and the longer one used on the Atlantic (1.48 km), but he does not explain the methods of their estimation (Freiesleben 1983: 126). According to Nicolai’s cartometric approach, its length—computed in comparison to a modern map in Mercator projection with the standard latitude of approx. $\varphi_0=40^\circ$ —varies not only between individual portolan charts but within each chart as well, and he rounded its average length to 1.24 km (Nicolai 2014: 263–264).

The length of *miglio* in kilometres—cartometrically derived directly from the georeferenced images of atlas sheets on which the Central Mediterranean is shown in comparison to a Mercator projection with the standard latitude $\varphi_0=36^\circ$ (to make it standardised to the remaining analyses in this study)—is 1.15 km (Vesconte’s atlas), 1.26 km (Bianco’s atlas), and 1.21 km (Agnese’s atlas), yielding a rounded value of 1.21 km. To compare them with Nicolai’s results, they need to be rescaled to $\varphi=40^\circ$,¹⁴ providing the values of 1.22 km, 1.34 km, and 1.28 km, respectively, with an average length of 1.28 km. These assumed *miglio* values were given only provisionally because it is extremely difficult, if not impossible, to determine its length with certainty. The first obstacle is the lack of accurate historical records about its length compared to other units of distance. The second obstacle are the misalignments of *spatium* (50 *miglia*) lengths in Vesconte’s and Bianco’s atlases, occurring after their coherent

¹⁴ The map scale of the Mercator projection at a given latitude (if the standard latitude is the equator) corresponds to $\sec(\varphi)$, i.e., $\cos^{-1}(\varphi)$. Therefore, the scale at $\varphi=36^\circ$ increases by a factor of 1.236, and the scale at $\varphi=40^\circ$ increases by a factor of 1.305. Since the starting point of rescaling is the Mercator projection $\varphi_0=36^\circ$ (with scale factor 1), the corresponding scale values at $\varphi=40^\circ$ are computed with a multiplication by a factor of 1.056.

composites are manually assembled. The third one involves unevenly sized images of georeferenced atlas sheets (due to their varying map scales), posing as a structural ‘geometry-disfigurement’ that hinders its determination by cartometric means.

6.2. (NON-)UTILISATION OF *TOLETA DE MARTELOIO*

*Toleta de Marteloio*¹⁵ in Bianco’s atlas (Figure 11) is displayed as a trigonometry table accompanied by *Tondo e Quadro* (circle and square) diagram that comprises eighth-winds resolution (64-wind division of a full circle, with each point having an angular range of 5.625° , or $\pm 2.812^\circ$). The table itself is made of two sections (left and right half), divided into three columns and eight rows each. Each row represents (an additional) quarter-wind angular-offset from a course desired (*avançar*), ranging from 11.25° (the first row) to 90° (the eighth row). If, due to some circumstances, the ship had to sail along an undesired offset-course, and if the sailors were able to measure the distance sailed, they could use the left section of the table to compute the shortest distance from the desired course (*alargar*) and the length of the projection of the offset-path to the desired course (*avançar*). Distances in the left part are shown relative to every 100 *miglia* travelled along the offset-course. The right section was made to assist in computing the relative bearing for optimal return (*retorno*) to the desired course and the length of the projection of the path travelled on the return course to the course desired (*avançar*). Distances related to returning to the desired course are shown in relation to every 10 *miglia* of the shortest distance from the desired course (Taylor 1957: 119–120, Nicolai 2014: 121–127).

Figure 11. The *Toleta de Marteloio* trigonometry table and the *Tondo e Quadro* diagram from Andrea Bianco’s 1436 portolan atlas. Source: *Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana*, Ms. It. Z, 76 (=4783).

In addition to a sophisticated understanding of trigonometric principles, a proper utilisation of *Toleta de Marteloio* requires highly accurate data on both bearings and distances as well. This means that its trigonometric shortcuts are practically usable in cases where nautical charts already exist due to the quick and simple measurement of angles and distances 'on the table'. The opposite case, in which the *Toleta* is used to benefit navigation in real time, and, even more, to create nautical charts from those computations, is less likely to have happened because accurate bearing- and distance-measurements were difficult, if not impossible, to obtain. In his historical account of late medieval navigational practices, Nicolai argues that the Mediterranean navigators of that

¹⁵ The name of this technique (known as *Raxon de Marteloio* in Catalan sources) for calculating the distance sailed has not been translated with certainty. The word *raxon* is translated as rule (Taylor 1957: 117) or counting (Nordenskiöld 1897: 53), and *toleta* as tables (Campbell 1987: 441). According to Adolf E. Nordenskiöld, the word *Marteloio* refers to a hammer (*martello*) whose blows were used to emphasize the time intervals and changes of crew and officer shifts onboard ship (Nordenskiöld 1897: 53), whereas according to Giuseppe Toaldo it means *the rule of the sea (mari logio)* (Toaldo 1782: 44).

era were not well-educated, that it was difficult for late medieval ships to maintain course in suboptimal weather and oceanographic conditions, that ship speeds and distances sailed were only estimated prior to the invention of the *Dutchman's log* and *English log* in the seventeenth century, and that the mariner's compass became widely used only after the first known portolan charts were already made (Nicolai 2014: 117–168, 349–387, 405–406). Moreover, a viewshed model of terrain landforms observed from a ship's deck reveals that sailors were unable to sight the opposite endpoint for nearly any cross-basin route (from a starting location) or track its bearing with a magnetic compass in advance due to their relatively low eye-height and the Earth's surface curvature (Marelić 2024c: 16–17).

Unlike earlier phases of portolan chart and atlas production during which there was no historical documentation of *Toleta's* presence among sailors' possessions (Pujades 2007: 464), Bianco's rendering of the *oikoumene* on a map in Ptolemy's first projection implies that he was exposed to knowledge that originated in classical antiquity and triggered the Renaissance. Namely, in the second century BCE, Hipparchus made the earliest known trigonometric tables (Boyer & Merzbach 2011: 146–149), and there is a likelihood that trigonometric principles were known even in the Old Babylonian era, between the nineteenth and sixteenth centuries BCE (Mansfield & Wildberger 2017). The existence of *Toleta* implies that Bianco had a sophisticated understanding of trigonometry, which was, according to Ramon Pujades, “a technique beyond the reach of many” even in the late fifteenth century (Pujades 2007: 464), but it was not reflected in the geometry of his atlas sheets due to inconsistencies in their anticlockwise tilts and map scales, as well as the significant geometric differences between the manually assembled composite of his atlas and his small-scale chart. Therefore, it seems unlikely, both historically and practically, that *Toleta de Marteloio* was a genuine late medieval Western European invention that was used to help cartographers create portolan charts and atlases.

7. MOSAICS WITHIN MOSAICS

Apart from variations in their rotation, scale, and planimetric accuracy, it is easily noticeable that each cartographer utilised a different approach regarding the areas encompassed within particular sheets and that their territorial extents differ between sheets. Vesconte, for example, ‘rounded up’ a large portion of the western area into one sheet (Figure 2), while Agnese did the same for the areas between the Ligurian coast to the west and the Levant coast to the east (Figure 6). Bianco, on the other hand, opted for the most uniform territorial distribution across the sheets (Figure 4), but this did not contribute to the increase in their accuracy in comparison to the other two atlases (Figure 10). Since it is not possible to assert the existence of any solid spatial logic according to which they made these selections (for example, the greater navigational importance of some sub-basins compared to others), it seems likely that cartographers' decisions regarding which areas are going to be encompassed within each sheet were primarily conditioned by the amount of available carrier material, its size, and the length ratios of their sheet edges, in accordance with which they individually tailored their map scales in order to fit in. The exceptions are sheets on which the relatively small basins were made to considerably larger scales, such as the Adriatic Sea (in Agnese's atlas) and the Aegean Sea (in Vesconte's and Agnese's atlases), presumably because the cartographers decided to exploit the relatively large surface of the parchment to be able to render their numerous islands in more detail and to inscribe a larger number of toponyms. The cartometric analysis, however, demonstrates that their planimetric accuracy has not been proportionally impacted by the increase in map scale. The accuracy of the large-scale *Adriatic Sea sheet* (12.3 km) from Agnese's atlas is greater than the *Adriatic subsection* (15.2 km) that, unlike the standalone large-scale rendering, contains large portions of the Ionian Sea as well, whereas the accuracy of its large-scale *Aegean Sea sheet* (12.5 km) is lower in comparison to the *Aegean subsection* (10.0 km). Both subsections are derived from its *Central and East Mediterranean sheet*, whose map scale is almost three times smaller (see Table 1). The accuracy of Vesconte's large-scale *Aegean Sea sheet* (9.9 km) is higher in comparison to the *Aegean subsection* (14.6 km), derived from his 1311 chart (Marelić 2024a: 154) that has been made to a 2.6 times smaller map scale (see Table 1) and contains a considerably inaccurate rendering of the Pagasetic gulf (Figure 3). Overall, there are discernible geometric differences between the central and eastern portions of Vesconte's atlas composite and his 1311 chart, and between Bianco's atlas composite and his small-scale chart (Figure 5). Such a multitude of variations on local and, even, regional levels between these ‘pairs’ created by the same authors should not have occurred if these cartographers had been provided with highly accurate bearing- and distance-data.

A considerably higher planimetric accuracy of portolan atlases is achieved by splitting them into cartometrically determined subsections (see colour-coded circles connected by dotted lines in [Figure 10](#)) that were discovered in the cartometric studies of portolan charts as well ([Marelić 2024a, 2024c](#)), and whose existence casts doubt on the medieval origin of both portolan charts and atlases for a multitude of reasons. The first reason is that the planimetric accuracy of the atlas composites remained similar throughout more than two centuries of their production. The accuracy of Agnese’s atlas composite, for example, is poorer in comparison to a composite of Vesconte’s atlas that was made more than two centuries earlier (see the horizontal dashed lines in [Figure 10](#)). The second reason is that the atlas composites’ anticlockwise tilts (shown by the horizontal dashed lines in [Figure 8](#)) remained relatively unchanged as well, whereas the magnetic declination across the Mediterranean and Black Seas shows noticeable temporal dynamics on a regional basis, with average values of 6.9° (year 1300), 5.6° (year 1400), and 2.5° (year 1500). The third reason is that, while individual georeferencing of atlas sheets cannot create composites devoid of graphical conflicts between neighbouring sheets, the individual georeferencing of their subsections results in smoother joins (compare the upper and lower parts of [Figure 2](#) and [Figure 4](#), and compare [Figure 6](#) with [Figure 7](#)). It is because the accuracy of atlas subsections (14.2 km on average) that were derived from their coherent composites georeferenced across the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas is, on average, 1.4 times greater in comparison to the average accuracy of their individually georeferenced sheets (19.6 km) and is approximately twice that of composites themselves (29.5 km on average). The fourth reason is that the territorial extents of their subsections—unlike their sheets’ coverages—are very similar in all three cases (compare the lower parts of [Figure 2](#), [Figure 4](#), and see [Figure 7](#)), which is reflected in their mutually similar *LSE*-computed rotations and relative map scales in comparison to their *Central Mediterranean subsections* (see colour-coded circles connected by dotted lines in [Figure 8](#), and [Figure 9](#)).

The significantly high planimetric accuracy of portolan charts’ sub-pieces was also determined by Loomer, who applied a 4-parameter Helmert transformation as well but used Fernand Braudel’s historical division of sub-basins ([Loomer 1987: 159](#)), and Nicolai, who applied a 6-parameter affine transformation and arrived at the statistically determined sub-chart division ([Nicolai 2014: 207–210, 240–243](#)). These authors also found that those sub-pieces show differences in map scale ([Loomer 1987: 159–165](#); [Nicolai 2014: 234–237, 259–262](#)). In this research, an additional layer of systematic map-scale errors was discovered, embodied in the sporadic scale-bar length inconsistencies in Vesconte’s and Bianco’s atlases that explicitly point at their inability to create atlases whose *spatiums* are of the same length after they are assembled into coherent composites. The results regarding the anticlockwise tilts of the atlas subsections are consistent with the previous cartometric studies as well. The earliest such conduct is Loomer’s thesis ([Loomer 1987: 150–151](#)). However, at the time, the only paleomagnetic data available were those collected by Jean Claude Tanguy on Mt. Etna ([Tanguy 1970](#)). In 2014, Nicolai computed the rotational values of five portolan charts on a sub-chart level, compared them to the CALS7k.2 paleomagnetic model ([Korte & Konstable 2005](#)) for the year 1250, and came across similar findings. Although he demonstrated that magnetic compass became widely used only after the first portolan charts were already made and that it is unlikely that it was used to observe their bearing-data, he points out that their anticlockwise tilts could have been added posteriori by Genoese cartographers because the general anticlockwise tilt of the charts corresponds to the value of magnetic declination in thirteenth-century Liguria ([Nicolai 2014: 414](#)). However, no solid historical evidence exists that explicitly addresses the underlying cause of their anticlockwise tilts. In fact, it appears more plausible that, before the early modern age, their authors were completely unaware of its existence.¹⁶ With the exception of the anonymous nautical planisphere made by the Spanish *Casa de la Contratación* (c. 1526-27) and Diogo Ribiero’s world maps made in 1527 and 1529, Battista Agnese’s chart of the East Mediterranean and Aegean Sea (bound in his portolan atlas made between 1543 and 1545) represents the earliest known example of cartographers’ awareness that the Mediterranean Sea renderings on portolan charts are not aligned with geographic north. The chart contains two vertical lines (parallel to the rhumb N–S) that represent scales of latitudes and stretch from the North African coast in the south ($\varphi=31^\circ\text{N}$) to the far eastern cape of Crete and the far western cape of Cyprus in the north ($\varphi=35^\circ\text{N}$). Those lines seem to be additions, but based on the calligraphy, they were plotted no later than the sixteenth century ([Astengo 2007: 194–195](#)). Their most problematic feature is that, while the latitudinal values assigned to both of them were made correctly, their lengths (and, therefore, the lengths of their one-degree intervals) differ because Cyprus was drawn further to the north in comparison to Crete, which points not only to contemporary misunderstanding of their anticlockwise tilts but to contemporary misunderstanding of their map scale as well. More recently, Marelić showed their anticlockwise tilts are comparable to the tilt of a

¹⁶ Christopher Columbus’s logbook contains the first clear record of magnetic declination. However, the so-called *travellers’ companion* devices made in Europe since 1451 (which combined the sundial and magnetic compass) and Portuguese sailors’ circumnavigations of Africa may have made it known to western Europeans decades before ([Taylor 1957: 172–173](#)).

meridian at Genoa ($\lambda=9^\circ\text{E}$) if the area were mapped in Ptolemy's first and second projections centred at Gibraltar ($\lambda=6^\circ\text{W}$). He proposed a hypothesis that Genoese cartographers may have possessed an atlas from classical antiquity, from which they copied and assembled regional large-scale maps in cylindrical projection while somewhat adhering to the orientational small-scale map in conic or pseudoconic projection (Marelić 2024a:151–155, 2024b: 158, 2024c: 17–19). In addition to the cartometric evidence, his hypothesis stems from three contemporary historical sources: Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi's instructions (1282) on how to draw the rough outlines of a map that geometry-wise resembles a portolan chart and was originally “drawn by the sages of Greece (Yūnān) and the ancient geometers”,¹⁷ the paragraph on the anonymous *Rex Tholomeus* portolan chart (c. 1360),¹⁸ and the excerpt from Benedetto Cotrugli's *De Navigatione Liber* (1464),¹⁹ both of which assert that portolan charts were made in accordance with Ptolemy's maps (Marelić 2024c: 19–20).

The accuracy of modern maps and charts depends on the accuracy of their geodetic and hydrographic surveys. This means that regardless of how their territorial coverage is broken up into smaller areas, accuracy levels would be the same or very similar if the survey were conducted with equal accuracy throughout the entire coverage. In contrast, the average accuracy of portolan atlases' subsections surpasses the accuracy of their coherent composites by a factor of two, a rule that also applies to portolan chart subsections in comparison to the entire portolan chart image (Marelić 2024a, 2024c). The only discernible differences between the examined atlases are the variations in the territorial extents of their sheets, whereas the geometry of their (manually assembled) coherent composites did not undergo any significant changes during the entire period of their creation. The almost complete absence of geometrical changes through time has also been computed for the coastline subsections that were cartometrically derived from those composites. Figuratively speaking, if atlases were observed as mosaics of physically separated images (portolan charts of smaller extents), this research shows that they are, in fact, ‘mosaics within mosaics’. It is because their subsections represent additional, underlying mosaics of images encapsulated within their composites, the existence of which their authors were most likely unaware, at least those who worked during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. Although the sheet division of the eastern regions in Vesconte's early-made atlas corresponds well to the subsections of its composite, his *western* and *Central Mediterranean* sheets do not. These two sheets encompass the *North Atlantic*, *West Mediterranean*, *Upper West Mediterranean*, and *Central Mediterranean* subsections in their entirety, as well as the *Adriatic subsection*, which he rendered as a separate unit positioned far to the west, presumably due to a lack of space within the *Central Mediterranean sheet* (compare Figure 1 and Figure 2). Given that these subsections appear to be the fundamental building blocks of both the *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart* as well (Marelić 2024a: 149–151), it is hypothetically possible that the first late medieval assembly of copied pre-medieval charts or maps took place decades before Vesconte even began drawing his charts and that he was another sequential, albeit highly talented, late medieval copyist of an already-established portolan chart template, perhaps even unaware of the true geometric nature of his cartographic products.

8. CONCLUSIONS

As far as is known to the author, this is the first extensive cartometric study of portolan atlases. It contains a comparative analysis of individual atlas sheets and their composites, a comparison of portolan atlases with portolan charts made by the same authors, and an intercomparison of doubly charted sub-basins made to different map scales. The results suggest that cartographers who created portolan atlases during the late medieval and early modern periods had a limited understanding of their anticlockwise tilts, map scales, and planimetric accuracy. None of the atlas sheets showing a larger area are fully aligned with the magnetic declination values from the period of their production, and each smaller-scale sheet contains portions of the coastline that were mapped to different scales, which means that they could not provide sailors with uniform navigational accuracy across the entire displayed area. Portolan atlases made by Pietro Vesconte (1313) and Andrea Bianco (1436) display the additional layer of map scale inconsistencies in such a way that their *spatiums* differ in length after the assembly of their coherent composites—a finding that explicitly raises suspicion about cartographers' true insight into their own products. This suspicion is further reinforced by the discovery of significant geometric differences between

¹⁷ For more information about Qutb al-Din al-Shirazi's writings, see Savadi & Campbell 2023.

¹⁸ For more information about the *Rex Tholomeus* chart, see Ruderman et al. 2023.

¹⁹ Benedetto Cotrugli's *De Navigatione Liber* is the property of Yale University, Beinecke rare book and manuscript library, Call No.: MS 557 (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/catalog/2005406>). The excerpt appears on pages 60v (image ID: 1029839) and 61r (image ID: 1029840).

the composite of Vesconte's atlas and his 1311 portolan chart, and between the composite of Bianco's atlas and his small-scale portolan chart bound in the same atlas. The existence of cartometrically determined subsections with accuracy twice as great in comparison to their composites, whose spatial extents, anticlockwise tilts, relative map scales, and planimetric accuracy have remained almost unchanged during more than two centuries of their production and geometrically correspond to portolan charts that were created before them, indicates that portolan atlases are medieval and early modern copies of some earlier-made cartographic sources.

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